

SPECIAL

**Scalable Policy-awareE Linked Data arChitecture for
privacy, trAnsparency and compLiance**

Deliverable D6.1

SPECIAL website set-up

SPECIAL DELIVERABLE

Name, title and organisation of the scientific representative of the project's coordinator:

Mr Philippe Rohou t: +33 4 97 15 53 06 f: +33 4 92 38 78 22 e: philippe.rohou@ercim.eu

GEIE ERCIM, 2004, route des Lucioles, Sophia Antipolis, 06410 Biot, France

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1 Introduction

Deliverable 6.1 'SPECIAL website set-up' is of type 'Other', meaning that the deliverable is the web site itself, rather than this brief accompanying report. Since Project Month 1, the SPECIAL web site is available at URL:

<https://www.specialprivacy.eu/>

This document provides an overview of the initial SPECIAL project website as it stands at Project Month 3. As expected, the website will evolve on an almost daily basis over the three years of the project. This evolution will be further reported in the forthcoming deliverables of work package 6 as well as via the project periodic reports.

2 SPECIAL website

2.1 Domain name

The *specialprivacy.eu* domain name has been reserved by ERCIM/W3C – the project coordinator - for 5 years. It has been registered on 17/01/2017 and will expire on 17/01/2022, over-running the project life time by two years. The registrar is Gandi¹.

The SPECIAL website is available under HTTPS (<https://www.specialprivacy.eu/>) with the HTTP traffic redirected to HTTPS. It rests on a server configuration tweaked to use the latest SSL best practices for recent browsers [<https://www.ssllabs.com/ssltest/analyze.html?d=www.specialprivacy.eu>]

2.2 Content Management System

The SPECIAL project website is built using the *Joomla!* Content Management System², a technology allowing the creation of dynamic websites, including update functionalities easily accessible to each partner in charge of uploading information to a specific section. Joomla! Also allows to produce responsive websites; this feature will be used in SPECIAL to allow access to the project website from all kind of modern devices.

2.3 Servers

The website is hosted on ERCIM/W3C servers, which ensures a long term availability of the information (well beyond the end of the funding period of the project).

For security reasons, six months after the end of the project and with the approval of the project coordinator, ERCIM will copy the whole website to a “static” version which will replace the online dynamic version. Content will still be available online but will stop being editable.

The servers use RAID hardware and redundant power-supplies to ensure high efficiency and availability of our services. Those machines are hosted in a secured machine room in Sophia-Antipolis, France. It is a limited-access facility, with air conditioning and uninterrupted power supplies. The systems are backed-up daily and are up and running 24/7.

2.4 Purpose of the website

The SPECIAL website is the public window to the project. It is the institutional website, meant to present the project, its actors, its objectives, and its outcome and achievements, to the public at large. It is also meant to keep visitors regularly aware of project news and progresses.

Other collaborative platforms exist elsewhere in the project work space to allow team work among the partners of SPECIAL and with associated EU projects and initiatives; these restricted platforms are not in the scope of this deliverable (refer to D7.1 and D7.2 for a wider view of SPECIAL tools and processes).

¹ <http://www.gandi.net>

² <http://www.joomla.org/>

2.5 Roles and responsibilities

Work package 6 'Collaboration, dissemination and standardisation' is led by partner ULD. Within WP6, Task 6.1.1 'development of a PR strategy and provision of dissemination material' includes in its latter part the set-up and maintenance of the project website. ERCIM/W3C leads this task, which spans the whole duration of the project and involves all partners.

It is therefore expected that ERCIM/W3C:

- Proposes a website platform and structure that allows the project to present its best image to the outside world
- Defines the processes by which all dynamic contents are easily editable by all partners within the proposed structure,
- Publishes contributions on the project web pages under the guidance and control of the WP6 leader
- Maintains the platform at the level of quality and availability expected from a EC-labelled web site

In order to honour these duties, ERCIM will rely on one of its in-house professional webmasters, as well as on a content manager who will be the link between the back office and the project partners. This content manager (Bert Bos, ERCIM) will work closely with ULD to review content that is being posted to the website.

All partners are expected to regularly provide web content and to continuously propose ways to improve usage and content of the website. To this purpose, a topic on dissemination is always included in the agenda of our monthly consortium-wide teleconference or meeting.

Content provision is the prime responsibility of the WP6 work package leader - Harald Zwingelberg and/or his team at ULD, under the control of the scientific coordinator who has a global vision of the project strategic objectives and achievements.

2.6 Information structure

The structure and navigation of the SPECIAL website is operational; it is articulated around the following main sections:

- **Home:** The home page of the web site
- **About:** Provides the general information about the project, such as:
 - Brief project fact-sheet
 - Overview of beneficiaries
 - Project plan and structure
 - Public deliverables
 - Contacts
- **Related Projects:** A linked list of EU projects and initiatives related to SPECIAL, in particular those members of the 'Big Data PPP' cluster driven by unit Data Policy and Innovation (CNECT G1) at the European Commission
- **Media:** where the following dynamic information can be found:
 - Project news
 - Press released and newsletter

- Dissemination material
- **Publications:** A list of scientific publications produced by the SPECIAL consortium
- **Members:** Private area for consortium members

The screenshot below shows the current home page design, together with the main menu choices and latest project news:

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Scalable policy-aware linked data architecture for privacy, transparency and compliance

<p>Lsz-Consulting "The Digital Enterprise"</p> <p>Event: Lsz-Consulting "The Digital Enterprise"</p> <p>Place and date: Vienna, May 3-4, 2017</p> <p>Title: Privacy vs. Innovation?</p> <p>Presenter: Sabrina Kirrane</p> <p>More Information</p>	<p>GI Workshop</p> <p>Event: GI Workshop, Wie sicher ist der neue Datenschutz? GI Fachgruppen SECMGT & PET</p> <p>Place and date: Frankfurt, March 10, 2017</p> <p>Presenter: Harald Zwingelberg</p> <p>Slides available here</p> <p>More Information</p>	<p>First Meeting in the Multi-stakeholder Series "Blockchain: Taxation and Regulatory Challenges and Opportunities"</p> <p>Event: First Meeting in the Multi-stakeholder Series "Blockchain: Taxation and Regulatory Challenges and Opportunities"</p> <p>Place and date: Vienna, March 15-16, 2017</p> <p>Title: The SPECIAL H2020 project: Applications of</p>
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The 'About' section gives a broad overview of the project, including basic contract data, partners' profile, and a summary of the Description of Work and of how it is structured. Public deliverables will be posted in this section, as well as contact information for visitors to find out more about SPECIAL:

Contact

Please contact:

- Sabrina Kirrane (Scientific Coordination)
- Philippe Rohou (Administrative and Financial Coordination)
- Harald Zwingelberg (Web Portal Coordination)
- or send email to special-contact@ercim.eu

Fact Sheet

Project Partners

Project Plan

Public deliverables

Contact

Legal Notice | Privacy Policy

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2.7 Website statistics

For the website statistics, ERCIM currently uses AWStats³, an open source alternative to Google Analytics. This tool is powerful, precise and complete. It gives most of the statistics and graphics needed in the context of a European project. The data are classified by years, months, days and hours. Detailed information about visitors, such as the country they come from, pages visited, duration of visit, keywords searched for, etc. is readily available to the webmaster for reporting purposes.

A statistical report of website usage will be included in the dissemination section of each periodic report, and presented at each review as part of the WP6 activities.

³ <http://awstats.sourceforge.net/>

3 Conclusion

At Project Month 3, the SPECIAL website is up and running, offering a clear and intuitive navigation logic, as well as initial static data that gives a complete overview of the project to external visitors.

Some dynamic content is starting to find its way to the SPECIAL web pages (news on kick-off meeting) but this effort is currently being ramped up with a view to having a completely operational feed mechanism within the next three months (by end of Project Month 6). From then on, the web site will leap forward in terms of frequency and quality of content updates. A first update on the evolution of the SPECIAL website will be available at Month 6 as part of deliverable D6.2 'Public Relation Strategy'.